

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE

Summary of I. Symposia with Representatives of R & I Structures

Deliverable 2.2

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EELISA innoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

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Executive summary

This document has been prepared for the fulfilment of delivery D 2.2. “Summary of I. Symposia with Representatives of R & I Structures” classified under the second work package of the project EELISA Innovation and Common Research Strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA innoCORE), hereinafter referred to as WP2 – “EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy”.

According to the grant agreement; two symposia should be organised under the second work package with the following objectives:

- compilation of significant research and development output in the last five years;
- discussion of future directions for strategic research areas;
- other potential activities complying with EELISA education, research, and development objectives;
- identification of thematic research areas of laboratories within partner universities

The aim of **the first Symposia, which was held in Istanbul on 16 May 2022 with the representatives of R & I Structures**, was to take the opportunity to bring the EELISA members and research partners together in Istanbul at ITU (Istanbul Technical University). The symposium took place one day before and parallel to the EELISA Research Based Symposium (RBL) with the aim of making connections, finding synergies and complementarities, that results from one project can benefit and feed the other.

Various studies were carried out to explore how cooperation among EELISA partners in the fields of research and innovation could be strengthened, particularly in relation to the first three objectives mentioned above. EELISA partners had the opportunity to take stock of the work done since the kick-off meeting on 1st October, 2021. Besides, the symposium served as the first large-scale event which brought people together physically and enabled better understanding of entrepreneurship capabilities offered by ITU and its ecosystem.

The symposium was accomplished in two-directions. Whereas the first part focused on a more theoretical approach, regarding the picture of the R&I productivity and capabilities of the EELISA Alliance, the second part during the afternoon focused on making connections at subunit levels. Connecting the EELISA researchers and promoting joint research activities is a key aim of EELISA InnoCORE and European and International Project Offices are the key player to meet this aim. Therefore, one of the panels was dedicated to the offices of the different EELISA partners to explore how to better interconnect their support services. Because the Entrepreneur and technology transfer capabilities are the key inputs of the R&I strategy, in a parallel session, EELISA explored how to combine its different resources and capabilities in the field of entrepreneurship and technology transfer, together with its brother project, EELISA Unfolds.

In line with the aim of the symposium three separate fruitful panels having different scopes were held under the umbrella of the symposium:

1. Online workshop: “Future directions on strategic research areas for the EELISA Alliance” with the objective of analysing the future challenges about and potential directions of EELISA research strategy.

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2. Panel: “How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA Partners” with the objective of exploring how European and International project offices (EIPO) of EELISA partners can better connect with each other and boost joint research activities.

3. Panel: “InnoCORE-Unfolds Joint Workshop” with the objective of coordinating actions towards a comprehensive entrepreneurship scheme, combining different assets and capabilities across the partners of the Alliance.

First innoCORE Symposium Program can be seen as below:

InnoCORE R&I Symposium Program | May 16, 2022

10.00-12.30	Opening Ceremony - Welcome Speech Online workshop: Future directions on strategic research areas for the EELISA Alliance		
12.30-13.30	Lunch		
13.30-15.30	EELISA innoCORE-UNFOLDS Joint Workshop (Part I)	13.30-15.30	How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners
15.30-15.45	Coffee Break		
15.45-17.45	EELISA innoCORE-UNFOLDS Joint Workshop (Part II)	15.45-17.45	How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners
19.00-22.00	Social program		

*All panels are scheduled considering Istanbul time zone (GMT+3).

Meeting	Time	Zoom Link	Meeting ID	Pass-code
Online Workshop: Future directions on strategic research areas for the EELISA Alliance	10.00-12.30	https://tu-edu-tr.zoom.us/j/99152671847?pwd=YIAzUjV4TW1YZ0ZmcjdWRko1U3A1UT09 or Click Here	991 5267 1847	489498
EELISA InnoCORE-UNFOLDS Joint Workshop	13.30-17.45	https://tu-edu-tr.zoom.us/j/97150884028?pwd=bFJTSm9zb1NBS1BBdJEva1NZd2Vodz09 or Click Here	971 5088 4028	961197
How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners	13.30-17.45	https://tu-edu-tr.zoom.us/j/98676267277?pwd=aTNNeXZuQW9hN3hweHlh cTBIiNW9Md09 or Click Here	986 7626 7277	148571

Figure 1: InnoCORE Symposium Program.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(Alphabetical order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

EELISA ACRI. Advisory Council Research and Innovation

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solving the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Proto-cluster. Groups of related research projects

EELISA Community¹. The EELISA communities are mission-driven collaboration and working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organisations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EIPO. European and International Project Office.

FOREU2. Forum of European Universities #2.

Focus groups: The research structures that focus on single research area

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

HE. Horizon Europe.

HEIs. Higher Education Institutions.

IPR. Intellectual Property Rights.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators.

Multi groups. The research structures that focus more than one research area

Output. EELISA scientific publications (journals, proceedings, patent...)

Pilot areas: The two-research area come from Grant Agreement

R&D. Research and Development

R&I. Research and Innovation

RSs. Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centers, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

¹ <https://community.eelisa.eu/>

RU. Research Units. Research units refer to analysis units, which are used in the analyses of research capacity. These capacities refer either to a structural entity, which is defined as “research structure” or “researchers”, who work in these structures.

Scopus. Scopus is the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature, offering journal articles and book chapters from over 21,500 journals and more than 130,000 books. Scopus provides a number of tools allowing you to analyse, assess and compare authors, citations and journals.

Scival. A web-based analytics solution with unparalleled power and flexibility that provides comprehensive access to the research performance of over 20,000 research institutions and their associated researchers from 230 nations worldwide.

SDGs. Sustainable Development Goals.

SS. Social Sciences.

SRAs. Strategic Research Areas. The research areas selected as “strategic” by the EELISA consortium at the Kick-off meeting

STS. Science Technology and Society.

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1. FUTURE DIRECTIONS WORKSHOP

Future Directions Workshop was planned under three consecutive sessions. The first session was designed to take stock of the previous and ongoing activities about the WP2, specifically a discussion of the main findings underscored in D2.1. The second session presented the main research outputs of the EELISA partners in the last five years, complementing the capacity findings and their variation across EELISA partners. The third and final session was designed to facilitate reflections on and discussions about current capacity, outputs and connectivity among partners to formulate a roadmap for the EELISA R&I strategy, involving both long- and short-term potential actions.

The presented reports in the first two sessions of the workshop were expected to contribute to the strategy development and road mapping for R&I COLLABORATION and COOPERATION between partners by leveraging strengths, harvesting opportunities and resolving improvement areas.

The workshop was held in a hybrid mode to ensure members' participation from all partners. Partners shared their opinions via zoom chat and their ideas on the Miro board simultaneously. The workshop took place on 16 May 2022 in Istanbul Technical University Istanbul – Turkey between 09.00 am (CET time zone) and lasted 120 minutes until 11.30 am (CET time zone).

ITU WP2 team underlined that D2.2 (deliverable of WP2 Task 2.2) is a living document, and they were still working on the complimentary report on R&I outputs, particularly on the bibliometric analysis. Results of Deliverable 2.1 & 2.2 will also support the research and education program of EELISA as a whole.

In the first and second sessions of the Workshop, ITU WP2 team presented the R&I strategy approach, principles, data collection and methodological processes, and the findings from the analysis of R&I inputs and outputs of each partner as well as EELISA as a whole.

In the final session, the participants contributed to the identification, clarification, and prioritisation of the factors that guide the R&I strategy, based on the information and discussions that took place in the first and second sessions.

The participants claimed their views on the pre-specified under the rubrics of Strengths, Improvement Areas, Challenges and Obstacles, each deliberated under short and long run. As one of the most important objectives of the symposium was to define concrete and collaborative action steps for EELISA Innocore R&I strategy, several specific actions were also proposed.

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1.1 SESSION I: Presentation and Discussion of the D2.1 report finding

In the first session of the workshop, Mehmet Erçek from ITU WP2 team informed participants about the D2.1 report finding (analysis of research capacities, strategy options by 11 Strategic Research Areas, complemented by the discrepancies of capacities between partners), followed by the discussion and feedback on the presentation.

Deliverable 2.1 has been prepared by both a top down (guided by Grant Agreement, Kick-off Meeting) and a bottom up (data and information declared by partners, iterative sharing and discussion on findings in strategic & operational meetings) approach. R&I inputs analysis included the research structures and researchers, presenting the research capacity of partners and EELISA.

The flowchart of the applied methodology in WP2 was presented as well as the methodological flow of WP2.1, which included mapping research areas of all EELISA partners.

Figure 2: Flowchart of WP2 activities.

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Methodological Flow of WP2.1 Mapping Research Areas of all EELISA Partners

Figure 3: WP2.1 Methodology as a process flow.

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During the session three key objectives for successful development of the EELISA R&I strategy were emphasised: 1- Defining concrete and collaborative action steps, 2- Leveraging key tangible and intangible resources of EELISA in the formulation of its strategy, 3-Identification of tangible and intangible resources and their potential configurations.

Hence to identify the strategic research areas for the alliance, WP2 D2.1 report aimed to map “the existing research capacities of each HEI following these strategic research areas.” and “existing research units across EELISA Innocore member institutions were designed following these principles”.

While doing that, we strictly refer to the key principles of EELISA which are structured around “collaborating multidisciplinary stakeholders around excellent research designs and outputs”, “the autonomy of researchers and research units”, and “a bottom-up approach towards identifying research challenges”.

The presentation proceeded with the analysis of “Research Capacity” in terms of “Researchers” and “Research Structures” including centers, hubs, units, groups, labs, institutes, with a research focus, having research outcomes representing a R&I capacity. A quantitative analysis of the Research Capacity of EELISA is simply presented as follows:

Figure 4: Frequencies of total researchers and research structures as the total capacity of EELISA for 11 strategic research areas.

These figures provided key insights about the “*identification of tangible and intangible resources and their potential configurations*” considering the EELISA.

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Figure 5: Radar plot of the research structures by strategic research areas.

The interaction of strategic research areas and SDGs were presented in the following Tables. The data collected from partners showed that the SRAs were not only strongly linked with the pilot research areas of EELISA, but they were also associated strongly with the EU R&I framework and sustainable development goals.

Table 1: Intervention matrix- linkages of Eelisa innoCORE research areas with EU horizon clusters.

Nr	Strategic Research Areas	Horizon Programme Clusters						EELISA InnoCore Pilot Areas	
		CLUSTER 1 (Health)	CLUSTER 2 (Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society)	CLUSTER 3 (Civil security for society)	CLUSTER 4 (Digital, Industry and Space)	CLUSTER 5 (Climate, Energy and Mobility)	CLUSTER 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment)	1 Sustainable and Smart Industries	2 Smart, Green and Resilient Cities
1	AI for smart industry				1	1		x	
	AI for smart city :					1			x
2	Connectivity			2	1			x	x
3	Social sciences and humanities		1	1				x	x
4	Digitalization		2		1	2		x	
5	Health	1					2		x
6	Smart industry and space technologies				1			x	
7	Advanced material science and engineering				1			x	x
8	Culture, creativity and inclusive society		1						x
9	Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment						1		x
10	Climate, energy and mobility				2	1	2	x	x
11	Natural Sciences				1		1		
	Scale: 1 - Multiple Topics Overlap, 2- Only one Topic Overlap								

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Table 2: Relationships of EELISA innoCORE research areas with UN's sustainable development goals.

Scholarly Output by SDGs	SDG 1: No Poverty	SDG 2: Zero Hunger	SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being	SDG 4: Quality Education	SDG 5: Gender Equality	SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation	SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy	SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth	SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities	SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities	SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production	SDG 13: Climate Action	SDG 14: Life Below Water	SDG 15: Life on Land	SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions
AI for smart industry									1			1				
AI for smart city											1					
Connectivity									1		1					
Social sciences and humanities	1			1	1			1		1	1		1			1
Digitalization			1	1					1		1		1			1
Health			1								1					
Smart industry and space technologies									1			1	1			
Advanced material science and engineering									1		1	1				
Culture, creativity and inclusive society	1			1	1					1	1					1
Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment		1				1					1	1	1	1		
Climate, energy and mobility							1		1		1		1			
Natural Sciences			1			1	1		1					1	1	

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Another important finding was the presentation of formations of homogenous and heterogenous dispersions of research capacities across SRAs and Partners. For example, SRA 3, SRA 11, SRA 10 and SRA 5 represented relatively higher dispersion and thus more heterogeneous capacity distribution across alliance partners. For SRA 1 and SRA 7, a rather more homogenous capacity dispersion was observed across alliance members. The degree of discrepancy across SRAs and alliance partners indicated potential connection, alignment and collaboration difficulties, and opportunities for better collaboration and alignment across these SRAs.

Figure 6: Partner universities' positions by research areas: formations of homogenous and heterogenous dispersions of research capacities across strategic research areas and EELISA innCORE partners.

The importance of a research area within a HEI can be evaluated by the weight ratios of those areas based on the number of research structures in the area.

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Figure 7: The weights of different research areas in EELISA partners.

Upon these findings, the findings about the total research capacity of EELISA per SRA is summarized in the following table.

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Table 3: Strategy options for research areas by their researcher and research structure levels.

Research Areas	Researchers Level	Research Structures Level	Difference Researchers - Research Structures	R&I Strategy Input	Strategy Action	Term
7 - Advanced material science and engineering	3	2	1	Potential	Support	Short
9 - Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	5	5	0	Improvement Area	Strengthen	Long
11 - Natural Sciences	1	1	0	Strength	Leverage for Opportunities	Short
5 - Health	2	2	0	Strength	Leverage for Opportunities	Short
4 - Digitalization	2	3	-1	Potential	Support	Short
10 - Climate, energy and mobility	3	4	-1	Question mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	Medium
8 - Culture, creativity and inclusive society	4	3	1	Question Mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	- Medium
6 - Smart industry and space technologies	3	4	-1	Question Mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	- Medium
2 - Connectivity	5	5	0	Improvement Area	Strengthen	Long
1- Artificial Intelligence	3	4	-1	Question Mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	- Medium
3 - Social sciences and humanities	2	2	0	Strength	Leverage for Opportunities	Short

Table 4: Degrees of variance and strategic initiatives for each strategic research area.

Research Areas	Number of Clusters	Level of Variance between Alliance Partners	R&I Strategy Input	Strategy Action
RA 1- Artificial Intelligence	3	Low	Strength	Connect&complement
RA 2 - Connectivity	2	Very low	Strength	Concentrate
RA 3 - Social sciences and humanities	3	Very high	Needs development	Complement & uplift
RA 4 - Digitalization	4	Medium to High	Question Mark (-)	Complement & uplift
RA 5 - Health	4	High	Needs development	Complement & uplift
RA 6 - Smart industry and space technologies	3	Low	Strength	Connect&complement
RA 7 - Advanced material science and engineering	3	Low	Strength	Connect&complement
RA 8 - Culture, creativity and inclusive society	2	Low	Strength	Concentrate
RA 9 - Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	2	Medium to High	Question Mark (-)	Complement & uplift
RA 10 - Climate, energy and mobility	3	High	Needs development	Complement & uplift
RA 11 - Natural Sciences	3	Very high	Needs development	Complement & uplift

Although these capacity metrics only reflect the overall research capacity and its distribution across partners, they nonetheless pinpoint essential findings regarding researchers and organisational units as inputs to R&D and innovation processes. In order to complement these crude capacity analyses

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with productivity measures, the research outputs of EELISA and its partners were also studied and presented in the upcoming parts of the report.

As a concluding remark, the existing plan was identified as a dynamic and iterative process. It was closely linked with strategic planning and timing of the outputs in other work packages such as the analysis and enhancement of Labs and facilities as infrastructures for an overall evaluation covering all dimensions of the EELISA R&I capacity. Also, platform and database creation for researchers, EELISA communities and clusters were highlighted as important priorities for building the organizational capital of EELISA. Here, the EELISA communities refer to the “mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges”. On the other hand, the “Clusters” are research and innovation-based working groups addressing the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities. Clusters will be created by means of a matching function included in the EELISA Networking Platform²)

The first part concluded with the discussion and questions on the D2.1 report content.

Some Feedbacks on the D2.1 presentation were as follows:

- **Updating the report with the EELISA Researcher Databases:** The use of a Central Research and Innovation System (CRIS) to collect researcher/research structure data was brought forward for further steps. After implementing this system, R&I input analysis should be iterated following the data entries in this system. However, for this action, data integrity and unity across partners' information systems should be ensured.
- **Avoiding the binding researchers' engagement based on their affiliations to institutions:** For exploring and analyzing the researcher capacity, it must be carefully considered that it should not be binding for a researcher to be affiliated with an institution. The workshop participants underlined that there were researchers from the different EELISA institutions and that they should be included in any project, EELISA community and/or cluster they wish to work or study with. Visiting scholars or adjuncts should be considered in this manner. The potential implementation of the CRIS researcher management system might help in this domain.
- **Research Structure Data Integrity Issues to be solved:** There may be a need for the iteration of the data collection on research structures, since there have been data integrity problems, and in data collection challenges from all partners (i.e. deliverable of WP4, Research Infrastructure).

² innoCORE Joint Glossary Research and Innovation Terms, pp.3

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1.2 SESSION II: Presentation and Discussion of the D2.1 Complementary Report on the R&I Outputs

In the second session of the workshop, Nihan Yıldırım from ITU WP2 team presented the study approach and findings about the R&I output of EELISA. R&I Outputs included the analysis of the publications, patents (IPRs) and awards/projects across SRAs, SDGs, partners and EELISA as a whole. The study on R&I outputs was a complementary study for D2.1 EELISA innoCORE Strategy of task 2.1 “Mapping of strategic research areas of all EELISA” was included in the tasks of WP 2.2 according to the Grant Agreement. To uncover current research and innovation outputs of EELISA and its partners, a variety of research outputs were collected for the last five years. This study included a bibliometric analysis of the outcomes by volume and impact with a dimensional classification by Strategic Research Areas (SRAs) and SDGs.

Figure 8: Online workshop: Future directions on strategic research areas for the EELISA Alliance (Istanbul, May 16 2022).

The analysis was also conducted according to SDGs covering the years between 2016-2021 and for 11 Strategic Research Areas of EELISA. Enabling a bibliometric analysis with higher precision, eleven SRAs were further associated with 96 pre-defined subtopics, and they were iteratively extended to 200 by the inclusion of similar words/terms/word forms.

R&I output of EELISA and its partners were listed under three separate headings and were presented in Figure 8:

- Scientific Outputs – Publications (2016-2021)

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- Publications Quantity and Impact Analysis (Scholarly Output, FW Citation Impact, Citation Count)
- Bibliometric Analysis: Co-occurrence, co-authorship, collaboration by institution, co-citation by SDG key phrases and SRA subtopics
- Patents and Citations – Patent Databases, Derwent, TTOs (Total)
- Awards and projects from Horizon – EU Offices, Research Project units, TTOs (in Horizon and FP6,7) – Total Project Number, Funds (decomposed to EU, National, Industry, other)
- PhD Students and Graduates – Thesis Topics etc. (Should we? If yes, from other WPs or by data retrieval tool to be discussed).

Based on the findings from Partners' research impact and production by SRAs, Subtopics and SDG Key phrases are presented at the end of the analysis.

The aim was to provide the research areas and topics with varying levels of impact and production of EELISA partners.

Figure 9: R&I outputs of EELISA and its individual partners.

Publications Analysis (Bibliometrics) Methodological Approach is shown in Figure 10 as a Process of R&I Output Analysis

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Figure 10: Methodology development of bibliometric study on R&I outputs of EELISA partners.

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Based on this process, and with reference to Prisma Diagram approach; the analysis below was conducted

- A descriptive analysis on the R&I Output indicators of EELISA in total, for research capacity analysis (using sources Scival-Scopus, Derwent)
- Quantity Analysis of EELISA Partners' Publications by SDGs,
- Quantity Analysis of EELISA Partners' Publications by SRAs
- Bibliometrics for SDG-based publication.
- Quantity and clustering analysis for Patent Outputs by SRA and SDG and Project Fund and Award Outputs by SRA and SDG are planned to be completed in collaboration with partners

As a summary of the quantitative analysis of R&I outputs of EELISA, some descriptive summaries are presented as follows:

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Table 5: Descriptive summary of quantitative analysis of R&I outputs of EELISA.

Output/Office Indicator Group	Indicator	Overall	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Volume	Publications	166,714	24,724	25,939	25,941	26,896	26,894	28,211	8,149
Volume	Publications	Scholarly Output (growth %)	8,7						
Volume	Publications	Scholarly Output (Open Access %)	54,66						
Volume	Publications	Authors	71,517	23,697	24,722	24,554	25,582	25,991	27,193
Volume	Publications	Authors (growth %)	9,7						
Volume	Collaboration	International Collaboration (%)	49,6	47,8	47,5	50	49,4	50,8	50,9
Volume	Collaboration	Academic-Corporate Collaboration (%)	6	6,2	6,2	6,3	5,7	5,6	5,9
Impact	Publications	Citations	2,001,557	544,999	468,956	404,333	307,612	204,497	68,387
Impact	Publications	Field-Weighted Citation Impact	1,4	1,51	1,4	1,42	1,39	1,39	1,38
Impact	Publications	Outputs in Top Citation Percentiles (top 10%, field weighted)	14,4	15,3	14,1	14,8	14,1	14,7	14
Impact	Publications	Publications in Top Journal Percentiles (top 10%, by CiteScore Percentile)	36,3	37,2	37,8	36,3	34,2	35,5	35,4
Impact	Publications	Citations per Publication	12	22	18,1	15,6	11,4	7,6	2,4
Impact	Publications	Views	4,220,225	836,254	814,519	794,831	728,716	572,333	413,450
Impact	Publications	Outputs in Top Views Percentiles (top 10%)	15,8	17,7	16	16,5	15,7	15,5	14,5
Impact	Publications	Views per Publication	25,3	33,8	31,4	30,6	27,1	21,3	14,7
Impact	Publications	Field-Weighted View Impact	1,34	1,48	1,4	1,4	1,31	1,23	1,25
Impact	Patents	Citing-Patents Count (patent office All Patent Offices)	3,856	1,862	1,273	715	301	54	6
Impact	Publications	Patent-Cited/Scholarly Output (patent office All Patent Offices)	1,493	530	465	288	165	39	6
Impact	Publications	Patent-Citations Count (patent office All Patent Offices)	4,485	2,006	1,321	782	315	55	6
Impact	Publications	Patent-Citations per Scholarly Output (patent office All Patent Offices)	26,9	81,1	51	30,1	11,7	2	0,2
Impact	Publications	Mass Media (Print)	1,212	140	172	427	177	260	36
Volume	Awards received in a different currency	Funding Body	USD	Native currency	Country/Region				
Volume	Awards	Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC)	713,006	55,943	United Kingdom				
Volume	Awards	Australian Research Council (ARC)	2,095,948	283,122	Australia				
Volume	Awards	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)	3,82,791	227,826	United Kingdom				
Volume	Awards	Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (H2020)	4,682,108	394,415	European Union				
Volume	Awards	Medical Research Council (MRC)	558,226	411,823	United Kingdom				
Volume	Awards	Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada (SSHRC)	2,311,618	302,674	Canada				
Volume	Awards	Awards Count	729	104	113	99	134	159	110
Volume	Awards	Awards Value (USD)	4,688,674,047	569,514,597	561,726,690	669,226,201	958,143,706	1,315,272,856	612,325,142
									2,494,915

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Besides, Topics and Topic Clusters of EELISA Publications were shared during the workshop as follows:

☐ Only show top 100 by Scholarly Output ○○ Bubble size: Scholarly Output of this Institute Group 📍 Bubble position is based on dominant ASJC categories.

Figure 11: Besides, Topics and Topic Clusters of EELISA Publications.

Taking SDGs into consideration, some highlights from the presentation were as follows:

- **The data collection for Patents and Projects/awards of partners is critical**, hence additional data collection from partners or retrieval from other databases was a discussion topic for participants.
- **The quantitative analysis of R&I outputs and the bibliometric study of the publications of EELISA Partners were completed.** These findings were submitted as a complementary report of D2.1.

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- **Retrieval of publications from Scopus** by SRAs was performed by an API developed by ITU. This API is sharable via a cloud platform by partners providing an opportunity to perform or iterate institutional analyses for cross-checking and validation.

An SRA-based analysis of the EELISA Publications and Volume Impact Matrices by SRAs was also shared by the participants:

Figure 12: EELISA Publication count per SRA.

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Figure 13: Impact and production of EELISA University Publications.

According to these results, the strategy Options and Volume impact matrix of Publications were formed. These strategy options were also discussed comparatively with the strategy options based on researcher capacity reported in D2.1 during the workshop.

Taking both R&I capacity and outputs of EELISA several important conclusions were drawn and brought to the attention of workshop participants. SRA 11-Natural sciences and RA-4 Digitalization were the best positioned SRAs of EELISA, as there was both significant capacity of researchers in these research domains and research outputs and impacts of these outputs were high. In SRA 5 Health and SRA 7 Advanced material science and engineering, EELISA positioned itself favourably as the capacity, and research outputs were also above average. In SRA 2 Connectivity and SRA 8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society domains, research outputs were below average so were the capacity measures. In SRA 3 Social sciences and humanities and SRA 1 Artificial intelligence research outputs and impact were below average although there seemed to be a significant capacity of researchers in the EELISA partners. In other SRAs capacity and output measures were evenly matched and were around average.

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Thus, as it is seen in Table 6, potential R&I strategic actions were also recommended based on the analyses performed. SRA 11, 4, 5 and 9 were considered strength areas, and the capacity and research outputs were above average. For these areas, EELISA would leverage its better-positioned resources and capabilities to seize opportunities. SRA 2 and 8 were identified as improvement areas, as the capacity and outputs were both below average in these domains. Thus, short-term improvement and revitalization might be necessary in these domains, considering the current capacity and outputs. Other SRAs, even though they had differences from each other, were identified as instead in the middle ground. Thus, further monitoring would be a key action for these areas to see if they evolve above or below average in terms of their capacity and outputs.

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Table 6: Strategy options for research areas by their researcher and research structure levels.

Research RA	Publication Count Level	Citation Level	Impact Level	Difference	R&I Strategy Input	Strategy Action	Term
1 - Artificial Intelligence	3	3	3	0	Potential	Support	Short
2 - Connectivity	4	4	3	1	Improvement Area	Strengthen	Long
3 - Social sciences and humanities	2	3	3	1	Question Mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	Short
4 - Digitalization	1	1	3	2	Potential	Support	Short
5 - Health	2	2	1	1	Strength	Leverage for Opportunities	Short
6 - Smart industry and space technologies	2	2	3	1	Question Mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	Short
7 - Advanced material science and engineering	2	2	2	0	Potential	Support	Short
8 - Culture, creativity and inclusive society	4	4	3	1	Improvement Area	Strengthen	Long
9 - Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	2	2	1	1	Strength	Leverage for Opportunities	Short
10 - Climate, energy and mobility	3	3	2	1	Question Mark (-/+)	Strengthen and Monitor	Short
11 - Natural Sciences	1	1	2	1	Strength	Leverage for Opportunities	Short

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- **Existing collaborations and co-authorships between Partners (based on data from Scival) offered significant potential in further developing within-alliance collaboration and partnerships.** During the workshop, co-authorships between EELISA partners and ITU were showcased to exemplify actual collaborations. Co-authorships between EELISA partners and ITU were showcased to illustrate actual collaborations between EELISA partners and ITU. Similar analyses can be conducted for all publication collaborations between partners by gathering data for each institution from Scopus or Scival databases.

A summary of co-authorship presents the human factor in the actual relationships among EELISA is shown below.

Table 7: Co-authorships among EELISA

Types of publications included		all publication types							
Self-citations		included							
Data source		Scopus							
Date exported		26 May 2022							
Year range		2016 to 2021							
Metric type		co-authored publications							
Institutions	École des Ponts ParisTech	Université PSL	Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa	Istanbul Technical University	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	Technical University of Madrid	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	University Politehnica of Bucharest
École des Ponts ParisTech	0	1123	11	2	3	16	0	1	0
Université PSL	1123	0	116	39	353	93	11	28	15
Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa	11	116	0	646	15	4	53	2	3
Istanbul Technical University	2	39	646	0	10	23	1	3	6
Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	3	353	15	10	0	23	3	24	12

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Technical University of Madrid	16	93	4	23	23	0	4	7	3
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	0	11	53	1	3	4	0	9	0
Budapest University of Technology and Economics	1	28	2	3	24	7	9	0	5
University Politehnica of Bucharest	0	15	3	6	12	3	0	5	0

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- An example of the data retrieved on co-authorships of ITU with EELISA partners is presented to give an idea on the subject:

Table 8: Coauthorships among EELISA

Institution	Co-authored publications	Co-authors at Istanbul Technical University	Co-authors at the other institution
Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa	659	19	82
Université PSL	41	32	49
Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	11	11	11
University Politehnica of Bucharest	6	8	11
Budapest University of Technology and Economics	3	1	2
École des Ponts ParisTech	2	2	4
Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	1	6	1
Technical University of Madrid	24	7	12

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Scival data retrieved on ITU and BPU was also shown in the following figure with a focus on specific collaborations between partners. Considering and exemplifying the existing co-authorships between EELISA partnerships, it might be possible to contribute to and motivate the process of proto-cluster formations and community building and/or engagements.

As seen from the example, such analysis can also provide a match with SRAs and SDGs.

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**Example for Co-authorship analysis:
BPE ITU CO-AUTHORSHIPS**

Figure 14: Example for Co-authorship analysis: BPE & ITU co-authorships. (Bibliometric data taken from Scival <https://www.scival.com/collaboration/currentCollabMatrix?uri=InstituteGroup%2F411>).

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- “The co-authorships illustrate actual research groups, and the partners must discuss whether EELISA can leverage these for expanding collaboration “without causing any entry barrier for researchers to any research area.”

This issue also needs consideration for managing both the influence and advantage of current collaborations. Moreover, it is crucial to provide opportunity for researchers to initiate research projects in new areas in which they could not be able to position themselves (due to their lack of network or infrastructure or resources) before the collaborative offerings of EELISA.

- **SRA and SDG Linkage was highlighted with the R&I Output data.**
 - o ITU WP2 team recommended the inclusion of SDGs as another dimension in the R&I outputs report since contributing to the SDGs was among EELISA’s main objectives. Below tables were presented in the workshop, showing the publication performance of EELISA contributing to each SDG.

Figure 15: Total Scholarly output for EELISA partners by SDGs.

- o As discussed in the workshop, SDGs and SRAs were not adverse or conflicting research dimensions, but rather they were almost fully aligned. The societal impact of the EELISA communities working within these SRAs becomes evident with their SDG linkages. Hence, the SRAs and SDGs should be dealt with together in finalising the R&I strategic directions of EELISA. Since the cluster lists or researcher databases

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were already kept with their linkages to SDGs, R&I output analyses conformed to the other structures of EELISA InnoCORE.

- There are many sub-indicators of R&I performance in terms of volume, value and impact. A further discussion on the indicators between partners can help both to current (AS-IS) situation analysis of EELISA research performance and also for future *performance evaluation* of EELISA (TO-BE), following the formation of EELISA communities and research clusters. This issue will also help put smart objectives into the EELISA research activities.
- DATABASES: ITU focused on the Scopus and Scival databases for the outputs. Scopus is preferred since its coverage is broader than WoS, especially considering multilingualism and the social sciences domain. However, the recommendations referring to the advantages regarding “openness” and “diversity” should also be considered in future steps. This issue should also be linked to “open science” principle of the EELISA. Considering even broader and more open databases of publications should be preferred in the upcoming stages better to represent the R&I outputs and impact of EELISA. Also, from an open science perspective, an iteration of the bibliometric analysis on R&I outputs can provide insights into the proximity of the EELISA partners to open access publishing.
- KEYWORDS and CODES: The R&I Output analysis was based on the Subtopics of SRAs, which were determined during the kick-off meeting and these keywords were expanded by equivalent terms from the Scopus database search. These keywords were used to extract EELISA publication outputs from the Scopus database through an API developed by ITU, as stated above. On the other hand, Scival assigns subtopics of SDGs automatically. Thus, no additional work was done to extract SDG-based publication outputs.
- IPRs: For R&I output analysis, measuring and creating an inventory database of IPRs of EELISA partners can be complicated due to ownership issues. For example, before the Industry Property Law in Turkey was enacted, the patents belonged to the academic staff even if the university’s infrastructures were used, but after the enactment of the law in 2017 the patents hereafter belonged to the universities. Thus, before 2017 ITU’s patents were low due to the enforcement regulations of the time. Similar complications might have happened in EELISA partners, which necessitates further queries about the number of patents for each partner and the involvement of TTOs, which work intensely on IPRs. Moreover, the valuation of patents is considered among the advanced issues that may be prepared in the upcoming steps. EELISA IPR performance by SDGs was also presented in the workshop according to their association with SDGs:

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UN Sustainable Develop...	Patent Asset Index*	Portfolio Size	Competitive Impact	Technology Relevance	Market Coverage
1 Not SDG related	476	724	0.7	0.6	0.6
2 SDG 03: Good Health and W...	153	111	1.4	0.9	1.0
3 SDG 09: Industry, Innovation...	118	210	0.6	0.7	0.5
4 SDG 11: Sustainable Cities ...	82	79	1.0	0.9	0.7
5 SDG 12: Responsible Consum...	44	81	0.5	0.5	0.6
6 SDG 13: Climate Action	37	99	0.4	0.5	0.3
7 SDG 07: Affordable and Cle...	36	101	0.4	0.5	0.3
8 SDG 02: Zero Hunger	23	15	1.6	0.9	1.6
9 SDG 06: Clean Water and Sa...	8	25	0.3	0.5	0.4
10 SDG 04: Quality Education	4	6	0.7	0.5	1.1
11 SDG 01: No Poverty	1	6	0.2	0.2	0.5
12 SDG 14: Life below water	0	9	0.0	0.3	0.1
13 SDG 05: Gender Equality	0	4	0.0	0.5	0.1
14 SDG 15: Life on Land	0	5	0.0	0.2	0.1

UN Sustainable Development Goals - Goals (lines) shows items 1-13 of 13, sorted by Patent Asset Index™ desc as at 5/5/2022.

Analysis based on 411 patent families active at 5/5/2022.

Data saved with the workbook on 5/10/2022.

All "UN Sustainable Development Goals - Goals" items not explicitly named in search are hidden.

Filter legend: Owner=(Budapest Univ. of Tech. & Eco., ECOLE DES PONTS PARISTECH, Istanbul Tech. University, PSL University, Sant'Anna School of Adv. Studies, Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa, Technical University of Madrid, UNIV POLITEHNICA DIN BUCURESTI, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg) AND SDG=(SDG 01, SDG 02, SDG 03, SDG 04, SDG 05, SDG 06, SDG 07, SDG 08, SDG 09, SDG 10, SDG 11, SDG 12, SDG 13, SDG 14, SDG 15, SDG 16, SDG 17)

14 total rows.

Analysis based on 1,135 patent families active at 5/5/2022.

Data saved with the workbook on 5/10/2022.

Filter legend: Owner=(Budapest Univ. of Tech. & Eco., ECOLE DES PONTS PARISTECH, Istanbul Tech. University, PSL University, Sant'Anna School of Adv. Studies, Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa, Technical University of Madrid, UNIV POLITEHNICA DIN BUCURESTI, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg)

Figure 16: EELISA IPR performance by SDGs.

For a more detailed and sustainable patent analysis, there was a need to create funding as either patents should be searched via paid databases or a systematic effort was required to collect data from partners. In case that the second option was pursued, partners could declare their patents by SRAs in a template to be prepared by TTOs and/or related units. For unravelling various IPR opportunities and challenges, WP2 teams, TTO teams and research commercialization units should collaborate. Afternoon session of Istanbul Symposium served as a medium by which participants from partner TTOs, innovation and research commercialization units discussed opportunities for better collaboration and sharing of best practices.

- Awards and Grants: For a complete analysis of awards and projects of partners, (both from EU, Horizon or other national/international sources) must be classified by SRAs and SDGs. Such data collection requires the collaboration of EU Offices, Research Project units, TTOs of the partners.

The total of awards and grants received by EELISA is presented in figure 17. However, additional effort is required to analyse awards and grants per SRA, SDG or Research Structures.

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Awards Value (USD) [ⓘ]

4,689M USD

value of awards in EELISA

[Learn more about this metric and how we capture funding data](#)

Awards Count [ⓘ]

729

count of awards in EELISA

[View list of awards](#)

Figure 17: Total of awards and grants received by EELISA. Source: Scival EELISA Awarded Grants page.

- The same challenge also applies to the PhD Students and Graduates – Thesis Topics etc. In case this indicator would be followed for R&I performance, there was a need to decompose PhD and graduate level studies according to SRA and SDGs.

Finally, the closing discussion of the session highlighted the “utilization of D2.1” report and “R&I output analysis” in the upcoming steps of the R&I strategy design of EELISA.

As a consolidation of the first and second sessions of the Workshop, the following topics were revealed:

An important note was on the re-assessment of the SRA-11. SRA 11- Natural Science outputs were positioned at the top of EELISA SRAs in terms of research capacity and research outputs. Yet, for an alliance focused on engineering discipline; natural sciences should be regarded as a vertical field which crisscrossed all other SRAs.

Additionally, the strategies to be followed for SRAs with uneven research capacity and research outputs were brought forward. Although no clear action set was determined during the symposium, EELISA governance was informed about the potential actions for SRAs with various researcher and research output levels. Besides, there were also strong SRAs with both higher capacity and outputs and SRAs with improvement potential through actions. EELISA actions on these topics should also have a strategic with the research strategies of the partners, and also with their research structures.

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1.3 SESSION III:

In the third session of the workshop, based on the information and discussions from previous sessions, the participants were facilitated by the ITU WP2 team for identification, clarification, and prioritization of the factors that guide the EELISA's R&I strategy. A template to facilitate discussions was provided, including Strengths, Improvement Areas, Challenges and Obstacles, each with a temporal focus (short and long term). In the workshop, which was conducted in a hybrid mode, partners shared their opinions via zoom chat and also simultaneously entered their ideas into the Miro board.

According to the discussions four important points came to the fore in the concluding session.

1-Striking a balance between competition and collaboration between partners

As the scientific research domain has moved increasingly into a competitive landscape among researchers and HEIs, a discussion in the closing session has raised the question of how to strike a balance between competitive and cooperative forces within the alliance. It is noted that collaborative tools and offerings of EELISA should be strengthened and communicated among researchers so that they would perceive a positive stimulus to join and contribute to the networks (i.e. communities, clusters) of EELISA. Offering tangible and achievable benefits for researchers to join EELISA networks is critical to not create an impression that participating in EELISA networks is a waste of time. Even though there exist discrepancies between partner in research capacity and outputs, it is acknowledged that allocation of resources on a competitive basis, especially in the early stages of EELISA networks, would have negative effects. Utilizing the partners' complementary capabilities and competencies can enable a balanced research opportunity in the EELISA community.

The R&I strategy should respect and enhance the current autonomous status of researchers but stimulate collaboration and joint project development among the researchers of EELISA partners.

2-Development and dissemination of solid networking tools and structures

As the most tangible added value of alliance building is creating synergy between partners and uplifting the total sum of individual contributors, facilitating networks and collaboration between researchers has become the hottest topic of the closing session. As seen in Figure 17 (Miroboard figure), participants in the workshop recommended using both online and offline tools to facilitate networking among researchers. The communities of EELISA is still being formulated, and the First EELISA Call for Joint inter-institutional Activities in Communities³ has been made by June, 2022. Clusters are also being built within the scope of INNOCORE. These are already structural leverages to facilitate and communicate networking for research. Yet, serious issues raised in this context were about *i) unclear understanding of different modes of networking structures in EELISA (i.e. the terms of community, cluster, proto-cluster etc.), ii) the lack of dissemination of these opportunities among partner researchers, and iii) the current disconnected status of EELISA communities and clusters, as each networking group had been separately developed.* Thus, to avoid misinterpretations of these collaborative modes, developing an online platform/tool was recommended, including all definitions

³ <https://community.eelisa.eu/1st-eelisa-call-for-joint-community-activities/>

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and glossaries available for users, and accompanied with a form for user-friendly data collection. The platforms in action are expected to be interoperable and coordinated to reveal the relations between the communities and clusters, making the embedded (tacit) linkages and collaborations explicit and codified to advance cooperation between partners. Directly related to the previous topic, acceleration of the development of the IT structure of EELISA and further development of online tools for matching researchers on a topical or project proposal basis was also recommended by the participants. Besides, many of the Istanbul Symposium attendees indicated that offline events should also complement online cooperation and engagement tools/platforms. In these platforms, researchers can also meet and build contact with each other during physical events (which are exemplified in the “Open Call for Workshops”). Lastly, participants also discussed whether to use existing co-authorships among partners as actual research collaborations and build on these linkages to facilitate new project proposals, especially at the earlier stages. Although the ideal form of network facilitation was understood as creating new connections among researchers who could not associate with themselves otherwise, leveraging existing linkages to create faster outcomes was also discussed as a viable action.

Complementary to the development and dissemination of researcher networks, another critical output of the closing session was the extension of researcher networks to all university eco-system. Beginning with adjunct or visiting scholars, TTOs, project management offices, research commercialization units, innovation hubs and incubators/start-ups should also be facilitated for better cooperation and collaboration. As a tangible outcome of this initiative, the workshop between TTOs of EELISA partners and the joint sessions of INNOCORE and UNFOLDS teams in Istanbul served to identify better and accomplish collaborative actions among respective stakeholders.

3-Management of Intellectual Property Rights across partners

Another significant point brought to the attention of workshop participants was the management of IPRs across the alliance partners. This issue indicated the listing of current IPs by partners, creating a joint platform by which each partner may enjoy access to and (if granted) advantageous use of these knowledge assets based on a possible consensus among partners. Besides, IP needs to be better managed through best practice repositories and sharing good practices as part of capacity-building efforts, where better-positioned alliance partners lever the overall status of others via such actions. (A successful practice responding to this requirement has been the Webinar of UPM Project Office.) Yet, challenges in the form of varying national regulations and capacity discrepancies were also discussed.

4-Building sustainable Alliance capabilities

The last but an essential point raised in the concluding session was about building sustainable capabilities at the alliance level. This issue is directly related to the further solidification of EELISA governmental bodies, their structuring and distinctive decision-making authority. As much of the intense work for creating an alliance structure requires systematic effort and process bound activities that are geared to last, development of staff functions of the alliance such as finance and fund management, IPR management, staff management etc. remains a fundamental issue to deal with. Although this point was explicitly raised to pinpoint R&I management systems and functions, it is embedded with all EELISA functions, such as learning and entrepreneurship. As a tangible outcome, it was decided in the INNOCORE-UNFOLDS joint workshop that many of the UNFOLDS outcomes

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could be directly utilised and integrated into the WP7 of INNOCORE to sustain joint effort activities of the alliance.

Figure 18: The Miro Board used in the Session III of Future Directions Workshop (https://miro.com/app/board/o9J_l0qfTKY=?share_link_id=617960986768).

1.4 The workshop findings from Miro BOARD - The factors that can guide strategies:

STRENGTHS.

The high capacity of EELISA in natural sciences, social sciences and digitalization can achieve results from the communities and clusters in these areas in short periods, and provide “best practices” for further actions.

OPPORTUNITIES:

Working towards SDGs, which are also linked to SRAs, is one of the best representations of the sustainability performance of EELISA.

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Communication and Connection

The options for improving communication and Connection in EELISA with immediate actions can be summarized as follows:

- Working with junior researchers who are looking to build and establish a network + including already well-established researchers who are open for and looking for internationalisation
- Working on already existing and emerging connections
- Developing clusters and ideas which researchers cannot develop or conduct on their own
- Collaborative Project Idea Generation and Proposal approach for NEW PROJECTS in EELISA Network
- Organising thematic workshops on SDGs to make researchers know each other and
- Utilize actual research collaborations and relationships.

Information Management

For Information management, many actions are already taken in different EELISA innoCORE work packages, such as:

- Protocluster proposal collection tool
- Providing network database to researchers for joint proposals
- Other IT platforms in progress.

IPs

As an option for utilizing open innovation approach and technology diffusion, EELISA partners can consider collaboration by IPRs. (Such as using the EELISA partnerships to reach technology solutions that may be required at a specific TRL level in Horizon and other project calls).

IMPROVEMENT AREAS:

Communication and Connection, Engagement

- The issues that need improvement in terms of communication, connection and engagement can be listed in the following topics: Until the Workshop's date, no proto-clusters were formed, though many proposals have been submitted. (*Proto-cluster* here refers to the "first Clusters obtained by manual selection starting from RPs uploaded in the excel file. This exercise is meant to setup the entries of the EELISA Networking Platform. Clusters will be automatically created by the platform in a second stage⁴).
- The events for matching researchers have been rare; therefore, further actions are required, such as organizing meetings with communities and project proposal owners. Some measures must be taken to ensure the relationship between clusters and the EELISA strategies.

Information Management

In the information management domain, some needs occur, such as:

⁴ innoCORE Joint Glossary Research and Innovation Terms, pp.3

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- Better knowledge of the different strengths of each partner, awareness of researchers about these strengths in terms of capacity and research performance,
- A better understanding of the definition of communities and clusters and the linkages between them,
- Taking the IT platforms (still in progress) in usage and providing data management and sharing.
- Informing researchers about the research and innovation activities and the outputs of Partners: It is time to make these data available, accessible and workable for others, (e.g. in the form of a connection tool so that researchers (esp. younger ones) could easily find a partner with shared interests and goals).
- Utilizing digital platforms for building trust and a feeling of shared belonging would be a basis for joint projects, which is hard to scale up by personal encounters.

CHALLENGES AND OBSTACLES

Communication and Connection, Engagement

The participants also report some challenges regarding communication and connection, and the engagement that can be provided through these. These challenges are listed as:

- Understanding and dissemination of the EELISA project to people,
- Reaching and persuading researchers to form communities and propose projects/building proto-clusters.
- Clarifying the rules and management principles of the communities.
- Explaining the added value of communities and clusters to researchers and creating awareness and willingness for engagement with EELISA (while there are already well-structured researcher communities with their own collaboration networks.)
 - Developing an understanding and approach for balancing the dilemma of collaboration and competition. (How to provide Coopetition (collaborative competition?) and inclusiveness in the same time?) Participants stated, "We will have to work on team building at two levels, both to get to know each other and to convince researchers to get to know each other through our intermediation." Therefore, the project teams working on the related WPs must perform in a multi-tasking manner, with parallel actions.
- Developing a researcher and research structure match-making function according to research preferences ("Tinder" for researchers with an emphasis on long-term relationships)
- Designing approaches and proposing solutions to make InnoCore attractive to researchers.

IPs

For Intellectual Properties of partners, EELISA innoCORE should provide some means of IPR management, protection and diffusion, such as:

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- Preparing the procedures to protect the idea of people before starting any project.
- Developing systems enabling partners and researchers to see the IP level of each university or partner for each WP or goal. (intellectual Property level or intelligence level of partners/ members)
- Determining the level of innovation or validation level of the patents or any intellectual property output

STRATEGY OBJECTIVES

Upon the discussions in the workshop, and the strengths, improvement areas, opportunities and barriers presented above; participants also came up with some recommendations on the strategic objectives:

Immediate Action

- Sharing data from D2.1 and R&I output by Partner with Project Offices and EU Offices and TTOs

SHORT TERM (Within the period of the project)

- **Communication and Engagement among academics and researchers and Project Offices**
 - Work on interventions for linking the researchers of partners who never collaborated before.
 - Organise a workshop based on a selected SRA during which the researchers can share their project ideas (connection to clusters), infrastructures and research outputs.
- **Information and Communication Management**
 - Defining different tools for making these connections: one tangible "tool" (We can use the budget for open calls for organising thematic events (to be planned), but more tools are needed.)
 - Comparison of existing databases and IT systems analysis to see how to combine different databases and integrate multiple systems for higher effectiveness.
- **IP Management**
 - Establishing a common portfolio (IP base as an intellectual capital inventory) organised by clusters for collecting and analysing patents susceptible to be furtherly promoted.

LONG TERM – (that may move beyond the project closure)

- **IP Management**
 - Establishing a Patents Database of EELISA for sharing / collaborating among partners, with solid definitions following the local IP regulations.
- **Management Frameworks**
 - Defining frameworks on EELISA Innovative Strategy Management, Human (Resources) Management, Intellectual Property Management, Infrastructure Management, Finance and Fund Management, Idea, Design and Technology Management, Collaboration Management

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2. PANEL: How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners

This panel was held with the objective of exploring how to better connect the European and International project offices (EIPO) of EELISA partners and facilitate joint research activities complying with EELISA research, and development objectives.

The workshop took place on 16 May 2022 at Istanbul Technical University Istanbul – Turkey, between 12.30 pm (CET time zone) and 1.30 pm (IST time zone), and lasted 285 minutes until 5.45 pm (IST time zone)

EIPO representatives of all innoCORE partners participated in the panel. The total number of attendees was 42. 28 participants attended the face-to-face meeting, whereas the rest connected the workshop remotely.

Within the first two hours of the workshop (13.30-15.30); EIPO representatives made presentations about their office structures, participation of institutions under H2020 and other international programmes, their internal structure of support for international projects, good practices, strengths and weaknesses. After presentations, in the second two hours of the workshop (15.45-17.45), the Miro Board voted on the good practices of each university. UPM presented their electronic database about international projects as a best practice.

Figure 19: The Miroboard used for EELISA InnoCORE I R&I Symposium - Parallel session 'How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners'.

After voting for the good practices on the MIRO board for determining priorities; the participants were divided into three groups to discuss how European/International Project Officers could improve collaboration based on the practices identified previously or with entirely fresh ideas that are offered during the workshop. First, second, and the third group discussed, “Could we offer or establish any potential EELISA-wide service?”; “How could our offices be better connected and increase joint proposals?” and “The barriers and challenges hampering cooperation” in respective order.

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After a 30-minute discussion on their topic, each group made a 15-minute presentation for the group representatives and the results related to short-term objectives were determined as below with the help of a moderator:

- Sharing MSCA hosting offers and giving them visibility,
- Organising MSCA and ERC writing days,
- Offering travel grants for researchers for working on MSCA / ERC calls,
- Sharing info for ERC synergy grants: similar to MSCA, the EELISA alliance can become an "advertising channel" for PIs,
- Joint training offer on transversal issues (open science, IPRs, etc) Following and complementing EELISA (e.g. EELISA course catalogue⁵), efforts in sharing resources, opening activities and putting in place joint activities for researchers and innovators have already started, including in transversal issues, e.g. EELISA info day 'Open Science in Horizon Europe, what does it take?'⁶ that took place on 4 April 2022 with the participation of OS experts from the EELISA partners, seminar "Patent search: strategic tools and examples", etc.
- Common repository with training pills for researchers,
- Gathering case studies / best practices: successful projects where there are EELISA partners collaborating,
- Organising of info days on Horizon Europe clusters,
- Training administrative staff on EU matters ("staff week induction to EU grants).

⁵ <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-catalogue/>

⁶ <https://eelisa.eu/events/special-info-day-open-science-in-horizon-europe-what-does-it-take/>

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Figure 20: How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners (Istanbul, May 16 2022).

The Results of the Panel on Joint Research and Effective Utilisation of International/European Funds

The panel has enhanced the understanding of each partner's differential status and capabilities regarding the EIPOs and related research organisations. The differences created opportunities to learn and collaborate for better orchestration of EELISA resources and capabilities and serious challenges to overcome for integration and alignment of such capabilities.

Challenges were grouped under three main topics:

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1-Barriers of researcher engagement

These barriers remain strong as researchers have limited time and resources for building new linkages under EELISA. Existing national and international linkages have substituting solid effects. Besides, tangible stimuli are needed to persuade researchers to collaborate in international projects and even more to motivate them to lead such projects.

2-Barriers to EIPO and external stakeholder engagement

Although EIPOs and research project offices are considered an integral part of an R&I strategy, some regulative barriers exist for them to align and integrate better with EELISA InnoCORE. This may arise due to national differences in EIPO 's autonomy or lack of capacity. Thus, engaging EIPO staff and increasing the devoted capacity of EIPOs for better coordination remains a barrier to better alignment.

3-Barriers to central decision-making and prioritisation

As OPI activities are not considered as a specific WP within the InnoCORE but rather distributed across several work packages, this creates a lack of motivation within and disorganisation across partner collaboration. Although the panel participants agreed that ERC, Horizon and MSCA represented opportunities for cooperation between partners, there was a lack of prioritisation among project focus and which activities to begin with.

The panel participants also offered solutions for these challenges. These solutions could be grouped under two headings.

1- Enhancing coordination and visibility of international project opportunities across EELISA partners

Panel participants offered the creation of systematic platforms among EIPOs to initially share relevant information about ERC, Horizon or MSCA opportunities for EELISA partners. In this way, it will be easier for EELISA researchers to become aware of different project proposals and onboard them easily.

2- Uplifting learning capacity of researchers and EIPOs for International Projects and Funding

To increase the share of EELISA in International/European Projects, participants also offered training and development programs for researchers and EIPO staff about finding partners and writing competitive project proposals. There may be specific seminars where participants share case-based success stories or EELISA-wide systematic activities to increase awareness among and engagement of researchers about different EU or International research projects.

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3. PANEL: InnoCORE-UNFOLDS JOINT WORKSHOP

This panel was held to coordinate actions towards a comprehensive entrepreneurship scheme, combining different assets and capabilities across the partners of the Alliance. The panel was organized with double convenors from InnoCORE WP7, and EELISA Unfolds project leader in order to explore opportunities for synergistic collaboration and complementarity creation between two ongoing projects of EELISA.

EELISA Unfolds⁷ is the component of EELISA that set to contribute to the transformation of higher education institutions into key players of the entrepreneurial and innovation ecosystem, as elaborated with the linkages between EELISA innoCORE and EELISA in Figure 21.

EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY

Figure 21: The Link Between three Projects of EELISA on three Dimensions of the European University (EELISA on Education, EELISA innoCORE on Research and Innovation, and EELISA Unfolds on Entrepreneurship)

The workshop took place on 16 May 2022 at Istanbul Technical University Istanbul – Turkey, between 1.30 pm (IST time zone), and lasted 285 minutes until 17.45 pm (IST time zone). WP7 representatives of all innoCORE partners and EELISA Unfolds project members participated in the panel. The total number of attendees was 40. 19 participants attended the face-to-face meeting, whereas the rest connected the workshop remotely.

Within the first two hours of the workshop (13.30-15.30); all EELISA partner representatives made short presentations about their entrepreneurship support infrastructures, incubation/acceleration programs for start-ups, entrepreneurship research and education centers and their respective activities. After the presentations, in the second two-hours of the workshop (15.45-17.45), the

⁷ EELISA Unfolds (Unlocking Full innovation capacity building and entrepreneurship) is an initiative led by EELISA members: UPM, ENPC, FAU, SNS, SSSA, UPB, and associated partners (ARTES4.0 and Fundación Universidad Empresa)

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InnoCORE WP7 leader and Unfolds project leader made short presentations about the aims of their projects, and what has been done so far in respective work packages. Following the presentations, an open discussion was made about integrating two projects better and enhancing the capacity of EELISA on entrepreneurship activities and programs.

The Results of the EELISA InnoCORE &Unfolds Joint Panel

The participants substantially enhanced their awareness and knowledge about EELISA partners' innovation ecosystems and what they can offer to uplift EELISA's capabilities in a mapping exercise. Physical participants to the symposium also visited ITU entrepreneurship infrastructures, namely ITU GINOVA (Center for Innovation and Entrepreneurship), ITUCekirdek (ITU Science Park's Incubation Center) and ITU Magnet (ITU Science Park's Co-working space for Scale-ups). The visit offered opportunities to provide an understanding of physical infrastructures of entrepreneurship learning, networking and laboratory use and entrepreneurship development programs and their outcomes.

Figure 22: ITU Magnet Visit- Brief about ITU Magnet Lab Activities by Tridi.

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Figure 23: Symposium participants at the entrance of ITU Science Park ARI3 Building (Housing ITU Cekirdek and Science Park Headquarters).

As EELISA Unfolds project will close in 2023 it will serve as a pilot for EELISA innoCORE WP7 activities, in particular for EELISA “shared infrastructures of business incubators”, “entrepreneurship action plan” and “EELISA-wide start-up initiative”. Successful activities listed under these headings will be integrated into InnoCORE and maintained. The project leader of Unfolds and WP7 leader of InnoCORE will have continued conversations about which activities will be integrated into InnoCORE.

During the closing discussions, opportunities offered by each partner for foreign start-ups, which are seeking international expansion and/or funding to extend their operations, are specifically examined. As start-ups in their early stages are specifically vulnerable and desperately in need of resources, the life cycle of startups has been considered an essential determinant for EELISA wide preparation of programs and support activities. To enable differential support activities and programs for start-ups with different maturity levels will be the next step in InnoCORE D7.3. FAU will prepare the data collection tool for EELISA landscape of start-up support in the summer of 2022.

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4. CONCLUSION

Three events which took place in the symposia revealed some essential highlights on the key learnings from the practices and activities, enabling or challenging factors, actions and strategy options and the lessons learned from EELISA (<https://eelisa.eu/>), EELISA innoCORE (<https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-innocore/>) and UNFOLDS (<https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-unfolds/>) projects.

Regarding the objectives of the first session “compilation of significant research and development output in the last five years” and the second session “discussion of future directions for strategic research areas” that have been mentioned in the introduction section of the report, the Future Directions Workshop ultimately served to highlight several important aspects in the development and implementation of an R&I strategy of EELISA.

Deliverable D2.1 EELISA innoCORE Strategy of task 2.1 “Mapping of strategic research areas of all EELISA” provided some key insights about the total research capacity of EELISA per SRA, “*identification of tangible and intangible resources and their potential configurations*”, and also on the homogenous and heterogenous dispersions of research capacities across SRAs and Partners. The existing plan from D2.1 is a living document with dynamic and iterative updating processes, closely linked with strategic planning and timing of the outputs in other work packages. For advancing the D2.1 iteration of the research capacity analysis with EELISA researcher databases, the data to be provided on research infrastructures from WP4 is defined as an action to be considered. This will help solve the integrity issues on the researcher and research structure data and for excelling the D2.1 towards a comprehensive and multi-dimensional analysis of the research capacity.

The research outputs of EELISA, in terms of publications, patents, and projects, show that the research capabilities are significant for most of the strategic research areas and SDGs. R&I output analysis revealed strong linkages between SRA and SDGs, presenting solid evidence of the sustainability orientation of the Alliance.

R&I Strategy Actions are recommended based on the research capacity and research capability analyses, which can be very useful in discussing prioritization and intervention planning.

The mapping of existing research capacities, research outputs and their distribution across EELISA partners has been accomplished, and the results are discussed with partners. With the completion of this task, opportunities and challenges to move EELISA’s research capacity and capabilities ahead have also been discussed. The Future directions workshop provided some important issues to be considered in further steps, such as striking a balance between collaboration and performative competition, need for the development and dissemination of interoperable and coordinated networking tools and structures, IPR management across the Alliance and building sustainable Alliance capabilities. The workshop discussions have, again, emphasized that creating synergy between partners and uplifting the total sum of individual contributors is the most tangible added value of the Alliance. Another important note was the need for elaborating on the open science-oriented R&I performance of the alliance perspective as a part of the EELISA R&I capacity analysis.

Moreover, the findings on the strengths regarding the high capacity research areas of EELISA, opportunities, challenges and improvement areas on sustainability focus, communication, connection, information management, IP Management unwrapped the strategic intervention options.

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Some of the short-term actionable options focused on linking, motivating and opening the way of including researchers through IT systems advancement and organizing inclusive and target-oriented events. In the longer term, the development of the management frameworks, including IP management, occurred as the prior needs.

There is also an alignment between the findings from the “Future Directions” workshop and the panel on “How to make joint research and apply to EU funds among EELISA partners” regarding the challenges or barriers to researcher engagement. The panel concluded on the results related to short-term objectives and the challenges which should be overcome by actions on the enhancement of coordination and visibility of international project opportunities across the alliance and on uplifting the learning capacity of researchers and the EIPOs for project calls and funding opportunities. As a solid norm underlined, EELISA community building or proto-cluster formation processes should be inclusive for all researchers in the Alliance, whether they are affiliated or not.

In conclusion, the major challenges include the difficulty in engaging researchers/in bringing researchers on board and the lack of systematic collaboration modes/methods across partners. As tangible outcomes of the InnoCORE have just begun to solidify, participants of the symposium often agree that the first challenge can be tackled with increasing dissemination activities and several systematic training/best practices sharing programs. The second challenge entails harder and multi-faceted problems. As it has been repeatedly reported in the resulting discussions of the panels, development and increased use of EELISA-wide IT platforms to identify, connect and engage different HEI stakeholders (researchers, EIPOs, entrepreneurship ecosystem, administrative staff etc.) is a recommended strategic action. Specification of central decision-making and resource allocation authority of EELISA needs to be better outlined to ensure prioritisation of SRAs and the modes by which collaboration should be put into action. Besides, better connection and alignment of communities and clusters will be crucial for the potential alignment of R&I efforts among partners. The panels about international research projects and entrepreneurship activities have clearly shown that best practice sharing and systematic coordination activities (online and offline) remain robust solutions to alleviate the second challenge on particular grounds. The mobility of researchers, experts, and students engaged in research and innovation should be prioritized for enhancing communication, collaboration, alignment and sharing of common values of EELISA. However, finding a way to apply the ideas emerging from the two panels, considering all work packages, and prioritising issues and actions remain significant challenges.

EELISA InnoCORE-Unfolds Joint Workshop provided a substantial opportunity for participants substantially enhance their understanding, expand their knowledge and increase their awareness about the innovative approaches and innovation-entrepreneurship ecosystems of EELISA partners. Enabled by this advancement, the workshop and visits helped them reconsider and imagine their possible offerings to EELISA to uplift the EELISA’s capabilities. Regarding the more synergies and coordination of EELISA InnoCORE and Unfolds projects, EELISA partners should focus under InnoCORE on a more in-depth mapping of entrepreneurial resources of EELISA partners so that we can know exactly what we can offer to each other. In the upcoming deliverables, WP2 team will move into specifying and solidifying systematic actions to enhance the R&I resource and capability sets of EELISA, with the integration of data from EELISA research labs, external stakeholder involvement and entrepreneurship ecosystem. Considering the “Link Between Education, Research and Innovation” work package, which is one of the work packages of the EELISA project, it is foreseen

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that the second innoCORE symposium will be designed in a way that EELISA Communities and innoCORE Clusters can be together and take these connections into account.

Another important highlight is the rising need for underlining the link between education, research and innovation. Various approaches which were put forward in the RBL symposium, which took place on 17 and 18 May, and “Future Directions” Workshop share a joint base for expanding the capacities and capabilities through shared actions. Especially, as covered in the EELISA project Deliverable 5.8 “Research and Innovation-based Entrepreneurship program”, entrepreneurship component is also strongly linked to the research and innovation-related actions, with an intrinsic educational emphasis both on the student and scholar level. The outcomes from EELISA Unfolds, and innoCORE have the potential to provide an actionable combination, synthesizing multiple pillars that can contribute to the European Universities model.

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